

Rest length and dilated time in five-dimensional spacetime

Dipl.-Phys. Roland Sprenger

October 4, 2025

Contents

It is shown how, based on the special theory of relativity, in a five-dimensional spacetime through geometric construction without oblique coordinate systems and scale changes rest lengths and dilated times can be determined. The rest system of the relativistically moving body is the observer's system rotated around the time axis into the fifth dimension. Superluminal velocities can also occur there.

Sections:

1. Introduction
2. Determination of dilated time and rest length
3. Justification of the construction method
4. Adjustment by the fifth dimension
5. Movement in \mathbb{R}^5
6. Observer in the reference system S'
7. Superluminal velocity at $t' < l$
8. Summary and outlook

1. Introduction

The script "Relativistic Addition of Velocities in R^5 " [1] takes up Theodor Kaluza's idea of a fifth dimension from 1921 [2]. In [1], unlike Minkowski diagrams, velocities are determined without specifying the changed lengths and times in five-dimensional spacetime. This script shows construction methods for this and describes the motion of a body in \mathbb{R}^5 .

Example 1: A rod of length $l = 3 L_s$ lying parallel to the x-axis moves at $v = 0.6 c$ in the x-direction to the right and passes the origin with its tip at time $t = t' = 0$ s. What is its length in its rest frame S' and how long does it take in S' for its end to pass the origin, i.e., for it to fly past?

2. Determination of the dilated time and the rest length

In S , the following applies
$$t = \frac{l}{v} = \frac{3 L_s}{0,6 c} = 5 s \quad (\text{see Fig. 1}) \quad .$$

3. Justification of the construction method

With
$$\gamma' = \frac{1}{\gamma} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

the following applies to the times
$$t' = \gamma' \cdot t$$

and for the lengths
$$l = \gamma' \cdot l' \quad .$$

In Example 1, $\gamma' = 0,8$.

From
$$t' = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot t \quad , \quad (1)$$

follow
$$t'^2 = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot t^2 = t^2 - \frac{v^2 t^2}{c^2} = t^2 - \frac{l^2}{c^2}$$

and
$$t'^2 + \left(\frac{l}{c}\right)^2 = t^2 \quad . \quad (2)$$

This is the Pythagorean theorem for the right-angled triangle in Fig. 1, who's right angle is at point A and who's long cathetus is the time t' we are looking for. Its short cathetus is only called l (i.e., not l/c), but because l is plotted in Ls, the values of l and l/c are equal: $l = 3 \text{ Ls}$ and $l/c = 3 \text{ Ls} / c = 3 \cdot c \cdot 1s / c = 3 \text{ s}$. Since the scales on the x-axis und the t-axis are the same, both distances are equal in length.

The physical reason for the existence of this right-angled triangle and for Eq. 1 is the constancy of the vacuum speed of light c for all inertial systems. This is because when the tip of the rod triggers a flash of light as it passes the origin, a spherical light wave propagates in the wave model, while in the particle model, photons fly in all directions, e.g., also into a light clock that is parallel to the t-axis at $x = 0$, see Fig. 2. If the light clock now moves to the right together with the tip of the rod at the same speed v , a photon in it travels the same distance on the relevant radius beam of the spherical wave as a photon in a light clock that has stopped at $x = 0$ in the t-direction, due to the constancy of the speed of light, see Fig. 1. However, the observer in S evaluates and measures as time t' in his reference system S only the component of the photon's motion parallel to his t-axis in the light clock moving with the rod. This results in the right-angled triangle O-A-B with the hypotenuse of length t , which satisfies Eq. 2.

The spherical sphere defines simultaneity – unlike in the Minkowski diagram, where parallels to the t-axis define simultaneity. Unlike there, however, the scales remain unchanged in this model.

According to Eq. 1, the following equation applies to lengths

$$l = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot l' \quad . \quad (3)$$

So
$$l^2 = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot l'^2 = l'^2 - \frac{v^2 l'^2}{c^2} = l'^2 - \left(\frac{v}{c} l'\right)^2$$

From Eq. 3, it follows that
$$l' = 3 \text{ Ls} / 0,8 = 3,75 \text{ Ls} \quad ,$$

so
$$\frac{v}{c} l' = 0,6 \cdot 3,75 \text{ Ls} = 2,25 \text{ Ls} \quad .$$

The term $\frac{v}{c} l'$ is therefore a distance s , shown in ochre in Fig. 1.

This means that

$$l^2 + s^2 = l'^2 \quad , \quad (4)$$

the Pythagorean theorem for the right-angled triangle O-C-D in Fig. 1.

4. Adjustment by the fifth dimension

What is remarkable about this triangle O-C-D is that the length l is parallel to the time axis and that l' also has a time component. It is also worth considering that the distance s in the basic, simple Eq. 4 must have a special physical meaning. In view of the possibility described in [1] of adding relativistic velocities in a five-dimensional space-time, it is assumed here that the distance s extends in the direction of the fifth dimension.

If we now reflect the triangle O-C-D on the bisector between the x- and t-axes and then rotate it by 90° around the x-axis (see Fig. 2), the time correlation disappears s and runs in the w-direction.

Fig. 2: Dilated time t' and rest length of the rod l' in five-dimensional space for example 1 with $t' > l$; time t shown in green, time t' in blue, rod length l in purple, distance s in ochre, rest length of the rod l' in red.

The rest length of the rod l' now lies on the line O-E in the x-w-plane. The observer in S therefore measures the x-component of l' or its projection onto the x-axis.

In a second example, section 7 shows the case $t' < l$. The distance s is then greater than the distance l , but is constructed according to the same rule.

speed $v = 0.8 c$. It therefore takes $t = 6$ s to pass the origin. With $\gamma' = 0.6$, the following applies: $t' = 3.6$ s, $l' = 8 Ls$ and $s = 6.4 Ls$.

Fig. 5: Example 2 as in Example 1 in Fig. 2, but with $t' < l'$; time t' shown in blue, rod length l' purple, distance s ochre, rest length of the rod l' red.

From Eq. 6, it follows that $v_w = 1.067 c$, i.e. more than the speed of light.

From $v' = l'/t$ or from Eq. 7 follows $v' = 1.333 c$, also faster than the speed of light.

Accordingly, the vacuum speed of light is only the absolute limit of all speeds in three-dimensional space, but not in four-dimensional space. The limitation only applies to the x-components of the four-dimensional velocity vectors.

8. Summary and outlook

The geometric methods shown for constructing dilated time and rest length in a five-dimensional spacetime are further evidence [1] for its existence. Further evidence could be found, e.g., in the interpretation of the redshift of galactic light [2], the interpretation of atomic orbitals as standing waves in \mathbb{R}^4 and the explanation of the entanglement of quantum objects.

References

[1] www.zenodo.org; DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10965934

www.roland-sprenger.de: Relativistic addition of velocities in \mathbb{R}^5

[2] www.zenodo.org; DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13336248

www.roland-sprenger.de: Universe without expansion and Big Bang